

A Study on the Immobilization of Toxic Metal Ions by using Prepared Kaolinite and Fly Ash-based Geopolymers

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Abstract

This research is a part of the research project of BOBLME (Bay of Bengal Large Marine Ecosystem) programme. The BOBLME covers 3.8 million sq km of sea area. The countries involved are Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Maldives, Myanmar, Sri Lanka and Thailand. In this work, sea water samples were collected from Gadonkani area of Myanmar Deltaic Coastal Zone seasonally. Sampling sites were recorded with GIS positions. Some physicochemical properties (pH, DO, salinity, turbidity, total hardness, total alkalinity, TDS, TSS, TS, free carbon dioxide, BOD, COD, orthophosphate, organic phosphate, total phosphate, nitrite nitrogen, nitrate nitrogen and ammonia nitrogen) were determined. Trace metals (Cd, Pb, Hg, As, Fe, Cu, Zn and Mn) concentrations of the sea water samples were measured by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) concentrations of sea water samples were measured as chrysene equivalence by using UVF spectrofluorometer. Oil and grease concentrations in sea water samples were determined by gravimetric-based method. Chlorophyll a contents of sea water samples were measured by UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Biological properties of sea water samples were investigated by membrane filtration method. All pH values of sea water samples ranging from 7.2 to 7.8 in the studied area are slightly basic. Maximum content of salinity (32 ppt) was recorded in the summer sample for sampling station (S5). The values of arsenic with range 1.19-1.75 ppb in summer samples were found under the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 3.6 ppb but the contents of rainy and winter samples ranging from 5.30 to 9.44 ppb were above the acceptable levels of 3.6 ppb. All measured values of Cd with range 1.20-6.06 ppb were below the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 10 ppb. All Pb contents with range of 4.02-8.11 ppb were below the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 8.5 ppb. All measured values of mercury with range of 1.10-2.26 ppb were above the permissible levels of 0.16 ppb. The values of orthophosphate, organic phosphate and total phosphate were found to be (0.016-0.352 ppm), (2.75-4.77 ppm) and (2.97-4.83 ppm) in seasonally collected samples. The values of DO, BOD and COD were recorded in the range of (4.80-6.20 ppm), (1.4-2.0 ppm) and (1.10-4.78 ppm). The measured DO values were within the permissible level of ASEAN standard (> 5 ppm) except the value of stations S4 for summer sample. Chlorophyll a distribution with the range of 1.207-1.981 mg/m³ was found in all of the study areas. Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) distribution over the sea water in the area of study was recorded as a range from 0.202 to 0.341 ppm. The concentration distribution (50.00-100.16 ppm) of oil and grease over the sea water was recorded in all of study areas. All numbers of coliform counts were found under permissible levels of EPA standard (<1/mL) for all sea water samples. *E.coli* in all sea water samples was not isolated for seasonal sampling.

Key words: BOBLME, Sea Water, total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs), orthophosphate, organic phosphate, total phosphate, oil and grease, chlorophyll a

Introduction

BOBLME Programme

Myanmar, Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Maldives, Sri Lanka and Thailand are working together through the Bay of Bengal Large Marine Ecosystem (BOBLME) project and lay the foundations for a coordinated programme of action designated to improve the lives of the coastal populations through improved regional management of the Bay of Bengal environment and its fisheries (Kaly, 2014). The BOBLME is one of 64 large marine ecosystems (LMEs) recognized world-wide, some of which have recently become the subject of the development of an ecosystem approach focused on sustainable management of biomass yields. The BOBLME covers 3.8 million sq km of sea area and includes approximately 1/4 of the world's human population. To implement the BOBLME project, there are four

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Components which composed of 16 Subcomponents. A key area under Project Component 4 deals with coastal pollution loading and water quality criteria, more specifically, the development of a regional collaborative approach to identifying important coastal water pollution issues and to develop remedial strategies (Kyaw Naing, *et al.*, 2012).

Aim

To assess seawater quality of Myanmar Deltaic Coastal Zone, to identify pollution hotspots and to consider remedial strategies

Experimental

Sample Collection and Storage

In this research, sea water samples were collected from Gadonkani area of Myanmar Deltaic Coastal Zone seasonally. Sampling sites were recorded with GIS positions.

Sampling Stations of Sea Water Samples

Figures 1 shows the GIS positions of sampling sites and Table 1 presents sampling stations and sampling dates of sea water. All samples are surface sea water (2 m depth) (Stutes, 2007).

Figure 1. Collection areas of sea water samples

Results and Discussion

pH, Salinity, Turbidity and Free Carbondioxide in Sea Water Samples

The pH values of sea water samples were found in the range of 7.2-7.8 (summer), 7.2-7.3 (rainy) and 7.2-7.3 (winter), respectively. The maximum value of pH (7.8) was observed in summer sample for sampling station (S₅). The measured values are within the permissible level of ASEAN standard (6.0-8.0). Most fish can tolerate pH values of about 5-9. So the observed pH value is suitable for fish and other aquatic life (Svobodova, 1993).

The values of salinity in sea water samples ranged from 24-32 ppt (summer), 20-26 ppt (rainy) and 22-28 ppt (winter) for seasonal sampling, respectively. The observed values are below the permissible level of ASEAN standard (36 ppt). Maximum content of salinity (32 ppt) was recorded in the summer sample for sampling station (S₅). The reason for increasing salinity may be the elevation of sea water temperature and low rainfall (Micheal, 2011).

Table 1. Sampling Stations and Sampling Dates of Sea Water Samples

Sample No.	Sampling Stations		Sampling date (dd.mm.yyyy)
	Longitude (E)	Latitude (N)	
S ₁	95° 13' 09.6"	15° 50' 18.8'	25.04.2012 (Summer)
S ₂	95° 13' 15.5"	15° 49' 07.8"	
S ₃	95° 13' 17.1"	15° 48' 56.0"	
S ₄	95° 13' 16.0"	15° 47' 00.5"	
S ₅	95° 13' 19.3"	15° 44' 54.0"	
S ₆	95° 13' 09.6"	15° 50' 18.8'	16.07.2012 (Rainy)
S ₇	95° 13' 15.5"	15° 49' 07.8"	
S ₈	95° 13' 17.1"	15° 48' 56.0"	
S ₉	95° 13' 16.0"	15° 47' 00.5"	
S ₁₀	95° 13' 19.3"	15° 44' 54.0"	
S ₁₁	95° 13' 09.6"	15° 50' 18.8'	01.11.2012 (Winter)
S ₁₂	95° 13' 15.5"	15° 49' 07.8"	
S ₁₃	95° 13' 17.1"	15° 48' 56.0"	
S ₁₄	95° 13' 16.0"	15° 47' 00.5"	
S ₁₅	95° 13' 19.3"	15° 44' 54.0"	

The contents of free CO₂ ranged 4-8 ppm (summer), 10 ppm (rainy) and 5 ppm (winter), respectively. The maximum value (10 ppm) was observed in rainy samples of all stations. The variation of free CO₂ with sampling stations was not found in rainy (all 10 ppm) and winter (all 5 ppm) samples of all stations. Dissolved carbon dioxide forms carbonic acid, causing a drop in pH whereas all pH values were observed in slightly basic range 7.2-7.9. This fact shows no pH drop as well as free CO₂ level can be sustainable acceptable range (ANZECC, 1992).

Total Hardness, Total Alkalinity, Total Solid, Total Suspended Solid and Total Dissolved in Sea Water Samples

Water is commonly classified in terms of the degree of hardness as 0-75 ppm is soft, 75-150 ppm is moderately hard, 150-300 ppm is hard, and 300 ppm and above is very hard. In this research work, the contents of hardness in sea water samples were found in the range of 1500-1680 ppm (summer), 410-650ppm (rainy) and 560-720 ppm (winter), respectively. Maximum concentration of hardness (1680 ppm) was found in summer sample for sampling station (S₁). It is due to the fact that increasing temperature can increase the solubility of salt.

The alkalinity concentrations of sea water samples in the area of study were in the range of 80-130 ppm (summer), 70-84 ppm (rainy), and 96-102 ppm (winter) for seasonal collection. The highest content of total alkalinity (130 ppm) was found in the summer sample for station (S₂). The rest contents of all sea water samples in the studied area were found to be within the permissible level of ASEAN standard (120 ppm) .

The amounts of total solid (TS) in sea water samples were observed to be 1353-1760 ppm (summer), 1154-1870 ppm (rainy), 1029-1740 ppm (winter) for seasonal sampling. The highest value 1870 was found in rainy sample of station S₆.

The contents of total suspended solid (TSS) in sea water samples ranged from 950-1325 ppm (summer), 488-730 ppm (rainy) and 402-747 ppm (winter). The highest value (1325 ppm) was found in summer sample of station S₄ and the lowest content (402 ppm) observed in winter sample of station S₁₅.

The total dissolved solids (TDS) contents were in the range of 403-717 ppm (summer), 666-1324 ppm (rainy), and 432-1188 ppm (winter) for seasonally collected samples. Many compounds depend on temperature to dissolve in water. Unfortunately, the maximum concentration (1324 ppm) was observed in rainy sample of sampling station S₆. The reasons for increasing pollution may be agricultural and residential runoff, leaching of soil contamination and point source water pollution discharges from industrial or sewage treatment plants (Sheppard *et al.*, 1970).

Table 2. Temperature, pH, Salinity, Turbidity and Free Carbon dioxide of Sea Water Samples

Parameters	Summer					Rainy					Winter					Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
Temperature (°C)	30.5	31.6	30.1	31.8	30.2	29.6	29.2	30.1	28.8	29.2	29.4	28.6	29.2	29.4	28.2	NC	-
pH	7.6	7.4	7.2	7.3	7.8	7.2	7.3	7.2	7.3	7.2	7.3	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2	6.5-8.5	6.0- 8.0
Salinity (ppt)	25	24	30	28	32	20	23	24	26	25	22	24	23	28	26	NC	36
Turbidity (FTU)	0.45	0.98	0.34	1.24	0.54	2.79	4.16	1.24	5.78	2.66	2.54	0.51	1.00	0.82	1.42	<700	15
Free CO ₂ (ppm)	4	6	5	4	8	10	10	10	10	10	5	5	5	5	5	NC	NC

Table 3. Some Physicochemical Properties of Sea Water Samples

Parameters (ppm)	Summer					Rainy					Winter					Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
Total Hardness	1680	1560	1640	1500	1580	590	410	560	470	650	1680	720	1680	1560	720	NC	NC
Total Alkalinity	120	130	100	80	90	74	70	70	80	84	100	98	102	98	96	30-150	120
TS	1650	1554	1353	1760	1712	1870	394	1816	1725	1154	1740	1430	1115	1029	1590	NC	NC
TSS	1200	1125	950	1325	995	546	648	730	515	488	617	747	580	597	402	NC	<10%
TDS	450	429	403	435	717	1324	746	1086	1210	666	1123	683	535	432	1188	NC	NC

Figure 2. Histogram of pH in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Figure 3. Histogram of salinity in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Figure 4. Histogram of turbidity in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Figure 5. Histogram of free carbon dioxide in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Figure 6. Histogram of total hardness, total alkalinity, total solid, total suspended solid and total dissolved solid in sea water at different sampling stations

Orthophosphate, Organic phosphate, Total Phosphate and Ammonia Nitrogen, Nitrite Nitrogen and Nitrate Nitrogen in Sea Water Samples

The orthophosphate contents were found in the range of 0.028–0.352 ppm (summer) and 0.016– 0.304 ppm (rainy) and 0.024–0.296 ppm (winter). Maximum content (0.352 ppm) was recorded in summer sample for sampling station (S₅). The amount of organic phosphate ranged from 2.78–4.58 ppm (summer), 3.34–4.77 ppm (rainy) and 2.75–3.99 ppm (winter). The contents of total phosphate were in the range of 3.02–4.61 ppm (summer), 3.54–4.83 ppm (rainy) and 2.97–4.02 ppm (winter). The highest contents for both organic and total phosphates were found in rainy samples for sampling station of S₆. Water with phosphate concentrations below 0.03 ppm is classified as oligotrophic, phosphate concentrations between 0.03–0.06 ppm are indicative of mesotrophic water (Mihajlovic *et al*, 2007). So the sea water in the stations that the phosphate contents are greater than 0.06 ppm is eutrophic. It may be the fact that excess nutrients drainage into the sea from the agricultural and urban sources of waste.

Ammonia nitrogen contents in sea water samples were found in the range of 0.02–0.04 ppm (summer), 0.02–0.08 ppm (rainy) and 0.02–0.04 ppm (winter). The highest content (0.08 ppm) was observed in rainy sample for sampling station (S₁₀). The rest of samples were below the ASEAN standard of 0.07 ppm. The contents of nitrite nitrogen ranged from 0.01–0.04 ppm (summer), 0.01–0.04 ppm (rainy) and 0.01–0.03 ppm (winter). Among these samples, the highest amount (0.04 ppm) was found in summer and rainy sample for stations

S₅ and S₁₀. All these samples were below the permissible level of ASEAN standard (0.055ppm). The seasonal variations of nitrate nitrogen were found to be 0.26-1.40 ppm (summer), 0.12-1.13 ppm (rainy) and 0.12-1.24 ppm (winter), respectively. The maximum content (1.40 ppm) was observed in summer sample for station (S₃). Most of nitrate nitrogen contents in sea water samples were above the permissible levels of ASEAN standard (0.06 ppm). So the sea water in study area is polluted with nitrate nitrogen. The reasons for increasing concentrations may be discharges of fertilizers from agro-based sources and domestic sewage.

Dissolved Oxygen, Biochemical Oxygen Demand and Chemical Oxygen Demand in Sea Water Samples

The dissolved oxygen (DO) contents of sea water samples in the studied area were found in the range of 4.80-5.82 ppm (summer), 5.80-6.20 ppm (rainy) and 5.60-6.10 ppm (winter) for seasonal collection. The minimum concentration of DO was observed in summer. It is due to the fact that the solubility of oxygen decreases with increasing temperature (Zweig, 1999). The measured DO values were within the permissible level of ASEAN standard (> 5ppm). The contents of BOD₅ were observed in the range of 1.4-1.9 ppm (summer), 1.5-2.0 ppm (rainy) and 1.5-2.0 ppm (winter). BOD₅ is of importance in aquaculture because microbial degradation of organic matter is a major sink for dissolved oxygen. Increasing levels of BOD₅ indicated organic pollution. All values of BOD₅ were under the maximum permissible level (< 15 ppm). Organic pollution may come from land-based source where located Gadonkani village doing the work of dried-fish and dried-prawn. The concentrations of COD were found in the range of 1.10-4.42 ppm (summer), 2.21-4.78 ppm (rainy) and 2.62-3.80 ppm (winter). Among these samples, the highest content (4.78 ppm) was occurred in rainy sample for sampling station (S₉).

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) test indicates the quality of oxidizable materials present in water. It is widely used to characterize the organic strength of waste water and contamination of natural water. COD is usually only significant where high concentrations of effluents from sewage and factory. All COD values of sea water samples were below maximum permissible level of ASEAN standard (<40 ppm). All COD values of sea water samples were below maximum permissible level of ASEAN standard (<40 ppm).

Table 4. Some Physicochemical Properties of Sea Water Samples

Parameters (ppm)	Summer					Rainy					Winter					Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
Ortho Phosphate	0.072	0.028	0.232	0.288	0.352	0.060	0.016	0.172	0.200	0.304	0.024	0.220	0.028	0.296	0.204	-	0.015
Organic Phosphate	4.14	4.58	2.78	3.15	3.30	4.77	3.97	4.27	3.34	3.72	3.99	2.75	3.99	3.30	3.36	-	NC
Total Phosphate	4.21	4.61	3.02	3.64	3.65	4.83	3.98	4.44	3.54	4.02	4.02	2.97	4.02	3.60	3.56	-	< 0.05
Ammonia Nitrogen	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.02	-	0.07
Nitrite Nitrogen	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	-	0.055
Nitrate Nitrogen	1.22	1.04	1.40	0.26	1.32	1.10	1.10	1.13	0.15	0.12	1.24	0.13	1.02	1.20	0.12	-	0.06

Table 5. Dissolved Oxygen, Biochemical Oxygen Demand and Chemical Oxygen Demand of Sea Water Samples

Parameters (ppm)	Summer					Rainy						Winter				Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
DO	5.64	5.82	5.20	4.80	5.22	5.94	5.82	6.20	6.0	5.80	5.72	5.82	6.10	5.60	5.84	>4	>5
BOD ₅	1.8	1.4	1.6	1.9	1.8	1.5	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.5	2.0	1.8	1.6	1.6	1.5	5	<15
COD	3.68	2.58	1.10	4.42	1.84	2.21	3.68	4.05	4.78	4.42	2.80	2.92	3.52	3.80	2.62	10	<40

Figure 7. Histogram of orthophosphate, organic phosphate, total phosphate, ammonia nitrogen, nitrite nitrogen and nitrate nitrogen in sea water at different sampling stations

Figure 8. Histogram of dissolved oxygen, biochemical oxygen demand and chemical oxygen demand in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Trace Elements in Sea Water Samples

In the present study, the arsenic contents in sea water samples were in the range of 1.19-1.75 ppb (summer), 5.30-9.44 ppb (rainy) and 8.40-9.36 ppb (winter). Among these samples, the values of summer samples only (S₁-S₅) were found under the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 3.6 ppb but the contents of rainy and winter samples were above the values of ASEAN standard and so the rest of sampling stations may be pollution hot spots. The concentrations of Cd in sea water samples ranged from 4.94-6.06 ppb (summer), 1.21-3.70 ppb (rainy) and 1.20-2.41 ppb (winter), respectively. At high water temperature, Cd levels increase and fish survival decreases under low DO conditions (Oziturk, 2009). According to data, all measured values were below the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 10 ppb. So the sea water in the studied area was not polluted from viewpoint of

toxic element, Cd. The contents of Pb in sea water samples collected seasonally were found to be 6.50-8.11 ppb (summer), 4.02-5.40 ppb (rainy) and 5.30-6.50 ppb (winter), respectively. The highest content (8.11 ppb) showed in summer samples of station S₂. From the measured data, all Pb contents were below the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 8.5 ppb. So the sea water in the studied area was unpolluted from view point of Pb toxic element.

The mercury concentrations in sea water samples collected seasonally ranged 1.22-2.26 ppb (summer), 1.10-1.71 ppb (rainy) and 1.21-2.01 ppb (winter), respectively. The highest and lowest contents (2.26 and 1.10 ppb) were found in summer and rainy samples for stations S₅ and S₇. According to data obtained, all measured values of Hg exceeded the permissible levels of 0.16 ppb. Therefore, the sampling stations in studied area may be pollution hot spots. The iron (Fe) concentrations in sea water samples ranged 164-212 ppb (summer), 129-153 ppb (rainy) and 117-182 ppb (winter), respectively. The highest content (212 ppb) was observed in summer sample of station S₅. From the results obtained, the distribution of Fe was found in all sampling stations. The zinc (Zn) contents were found to be 31-51 ppb (summer), 13-40 ppb (rainy) and 25-36 ppb (winter) in seasonally collected sea water samples, respectively. The maximum content (51 ppb) was observed in summer sample of station S₃. Among the trace metals measured, the rest of elements (Cu and Mn) were not detected in all sea water samples for both seasonally and yearly collected samples. From study area results, the concentration variations of As, Cd, Pb, Hg, Fe and Zn were found in seasonally collected samples. This occurrence may be related with pesticides from agro-based and industrial sources.

Chlorophyll, Total petroleum hydrocarbon, Oil and Grease in sea water samples

In this study, the contents of chlorophyll *a* were observed in the range of 1.307-1.694 mg/m³ (summer), 1.207-1.869 mg/m³ (rainy) and 1.409-1.981 mg/m³ (winter) for seasonal sampling. Winter samples showed the highest concentration (1.981 mg/m³) in sampling station S₁₄. The lowest content (1.207 mg/m³) was found in rainy sample for sampling station S₈. Chlorophyll concentration is one of the key indices in the study of the health status of any natural marine ecosystem (Vernet, 1983). According to data observed, sea water in the studied region is unpolluted with chlorophyll. The concentrations of total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs) were in the range of 0.202-0.282 ppm (summer), 0.298-0.318 ppm (rainy) and 0.302-0.341 ppm (winter). Summer samples showed the lowest concentration (0.202 ppm) in sampling station of S₅. The highest content (0.341 ppm) was found in winter sample for sampling station of S₁₅. TPHs concentrations in the sea water varied with seasons, showing a decreasing order of winter>rainy>summer. Over the seasonal period, TPHs in sea water samples steadily decreased. The highest values obtained were at sampling station S₁₅ where shipping activities and land-based waste water discharges were the major sources of pollution. The obtained results provided the background information on the extent of TPHs concentration in the sea water and pointed out the need to further control TPHs pollution in Deltaic Coastal Zone. In the present work, the concentrations of oil and grease were in the range of 50.00-50.10 ppm (summer), 50.01-50.13 ppm (rainy) and 100.00-100.16 ppm (winter) in seasonally collected samples. From study area data, all values of oil and grease are under the permissible level of ASEAN standard (140 ppm). Over the seasonal period, oil and grease concentrations in sea water samples distinctly increased from summer and rainy samples to winter samples. The distribution of oil and grease was found at all sampling stations where shipping activities and land-based waste water discharges were the major sources of pollution (Yang, 2009).

Total Coliform and *Escherichia coli* in sea water samples

In the present study, the numbers of total coliform were detected as 5 MPN/100 mL in all sea water samples (summer), as 9 MPN/100 mL in all sea water samples (rainy) and as 6 MPN/100 mL in all sea water samples (winter) for seasonal sampling. The lowest and highest counts were found in summer sampling and in rainy sampling. All numbers of coliform counts were found under permissible levels of EPA standard (<1/mL) for all sea water samples. Therefore, the sea water samples in studied areas were not polluted with bacteria (coliform and *E. coli*).

Table 6. Trace Element Contents in Sea Water Samples

Elements (ppb)	Summer					Rainy					Winter					Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
As	1.64	1.28	1.19	1.36	1.75	7.35	9.44	6.38	5.30	6.42	8.76	8.91	9.21	8.40	9.36	69	3.6
Cd	6.06	6.01	5.04	4.94	5.98	3.70	2.40	1.21	1.40	1.81	2.41	1.71	1.20	2.40	1.50	40	10
Pb	7.90	8.11	6.9	6.50	7.21	4.20	5.40	4.21	4.02	5.32	5.42	5.30	5.80	6.50	5.31	210	8.5
Hg	1.50	2.10	1.82	1.22	2.26	1.71	1.10	1.31	1.70	1.11	1.21	1.50	2.01	1.80	1.71	1.8	0.16
Cu	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	4.8	8									
Fe	171	186	164	203	212	129	134	153	139	142	117	128	124	168	182	-	NC
Zn	31	44	51	50	47	40	26	13	34	27	25	30	27	31	36	90	NC
Mn	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	-	NC									

Table 7. Some Physicochemical Properties of Sea Water Samples

Parameters	Summer					Rainy					Winter					Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
Chlorophyll <i>a</i> (mg/m ³)	1.578	1.307	1.407	1.421	1.694	1.608	1.809	1.207	1.869	1.605	1.409	1.607	1.501	1.981	1.814	NC	2
TPHs (ppm)	0.208	0.215	0.282	0.228	0.202	0.301	0.298	0.304	0.311	0.318	0.332	0.302	0.314	0.317	0.341	NC	NC
Oil and Grease (ppm)	50.00	50.01	50.03	50.01	50.10	50.01	50.05	50.04	50.10	50.13	100.02	100.00	100.12	100.04	100.16	NC	140

Table 8. Coliform and *Escherichia coli* in Sea Water Samples

Parameters	Summer					Rainy					Winter					Standards	
	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅	EPA (2009)	ASEAN (2010)
Coliform (MPN/10mL)	5	5	5	5	5	9	9	9	9	9	6	6	6	6	6	NC	<1/mL
<i>E. coli</i> (MPN/10mL)	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NI	NC	<1/mL									

NI = Not Isolated; NC = Not of Concerns; MPN = Most Probable Number

Figure 9. Histogram of trace element contents in sea water at different sampling stations

Figure 10. Histogram of chlorophyll *a* in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Figure 11. Histogram of total petroleum hydrocarbons in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Figure 12. Histogram of oil and grease in sea water as a function of sampling stations

Conclusion

The highest value of pH (7.8) was observed in summer sample of sampling station S₅. Most fish can tolerate pH values of about 5-9. So the observed pH value is suitable for fish and other aquatic life. The maximum content of salinity (32 ppt) was recorded in the summer sample for sampling station (S₅). All measured values of turbidity (0.24-5.78 FTU) in sea water samples were under the permissible level of ASEAN standard (15 FTU). The variation of free CO₂ with sampling stations was not found in rainy (10 ppm) and winter (5 ppm) samples for all stations. The highest concentration of hardness was 1680 ppm recorded in summer sample for sampling station S₁. The highest content of total alkalinity (130 ppm) was observed in the summer sample for station of S₂. The variation of free CO₂ with sampling stations was not found in rainy (10 ppm) and winter (5 ppm) samples for all stations.

Unfortunately, the maximum concentration of TDS (1324 ppm) was observed in rainy sample of sampling station S₆. The highest value of TSS (1325 ppm) was found in summer sample of station S₄ and the lowest content (402 ppm) observed in winter sample of station S₁₅. The highest value of TS 1870 ppm was found in rainy sample of station S₆. All measured values of Cd (1.20-6.06 ppb) were below the permissible levels of ASEAN standard of 10 ppb. The highest Pb content (8.11 ppb) was found in summer sample of sampling station S₂. The highest value of mercury (2.26 ppb) was observed in summer sample of station S₅. The highest content of Fe (212 ppb) was observed in summer sample of station S₅. The maximum content of Zn (51 ppb) was observed in summer sample of station S₃. Among the trace metals measured, the rest of studied elements (Cu and Mn) were not detected in all sea water samples for seasonally collected samples. The maximum content of orthophosphate (0.352 ppm) was found in summer sample for sampling station (S₅). The highest contents for both organic and total phosphates (4.77 ppm and 4.83 ppm) were observed in rainy samples for sampling station of S₆. The highest content of ammonia nitrogen was 0.08 ppm recorded in rainy sample for sampling station of S₁₀. The highest amount of nitrite nitrogen (0.04 ppm) was found in rainy sample for station of S₁₀. The maximum content of nitrate nitrogen (1.40 ppm) was recorded in summer sample for station of S₃. The minimum value of DO (4.80 ppm) was observed in summer for sampling station S₄. All values of BOD₅ for seasonally collected samples were under the maximum permissible level (< 15 ppm). All COD values of sea water samples were below acceptable level of ASEAN standard (<40 ppm).

The lowest content of chlorophyll *a* (1.207 mg/m³) was found in rainy sample of sampling station S₈. Summer samples showed the lowest concentration of TPHs (0.202 ppm) in sampling station of S₅. The highest content (0.341 ppm) was recorded in winter sample for sampling station of S₁₅. The observed results provided the background information on the extent of TPHs concentration in the sea water and highlighted the need to further control TPHs pollution in Deltaic Coastal Zone. The lowest concentration of oil and grease (50.00 ppm) was found in summer samples for station of S₁. The highest content (100.16 ppm) was recorded in winter sample for sampling station of S₁₅. The profound variation was recorded in winter samples. Over the seasonal period, oil and grease concentrations in sea water samples distinctly increased from summer and rainy samples to winter samples. *E.coli* was not isolated in all sea water samples for seasonal sampling. All numbers of coliform counts were found under permissible levels of EPA standard (<1/mL) for all sea water samples. Therefore, the sea water samples in studied areas were not polluted with bacteria (coliform and *E.coli*).

Finally, it could be deduced that the maintenance of coastal pollution loading and water quality criteria is very important for aquatic life in BOB (Bay of Bengal) areas

including Myanmar to enhance food security and reduce poverty for coastal communities in Bay of Bengal region.

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